

AN ANALYSIS – ROLE OF GOVERNMENT IN APPLAUDING COMPANIES CONTRIBUTING CSR

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Abstract

The concept of Corporate Social Responsibility was introduced in India as a mandatory provision from April 1, 2014, through the Companies Act, 2013, with an objective of making the business organisations namely companies to contribute something out of its profits towards the Sustainable Development and earn valuable goodwill from the members of public. This introspection or analysis tries to understand the achievement made by the Indian Industries in the form of goodwill earned out of contributions to the CSR and the lack of appreciation or acknowledgment on the part of Government Departments or Organisations in doing so.

Keywords: *Corporate Social Responsibility, Sustainable Development, Goodwill, Government Departments and Organisations.*

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Introduction

Every commercial business concern including a Company has primary objective of maximisation of income and wealth of its Shareholders and others interested in the companies and for the same they struggle and thrive. In the process of their task, they utilise various resources from the society and pay the reasonable fees / compensation for using the same. In process of doing the business they follow and comply all the legal and semi legal obligations created by the Law of the Land. In India, we have several rules and regulations created by various Government as well as quasi-government bodies. Besides, we also have National Voluntary Guidelines on Social, Environmental & Economic Responsibilities of Business (popularly known as NVGs), which are applicable to all the business enterprises irrespective of its Size, Capital Contribution or Location, Then, the

question arises what is the need for CSR or why CSR? An additional burden on otherwise troubled Indian Industries troubled due to multiple compliances framed by the Law Makers, would result in lots of hardships?

Meaning of CSR - Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a self-regulating business model that helps a company be socially accountable—to itself, its stakeholders, and the public. By practicing corporate social responsibility, also called corporate citizenship, companies can be conscious of the kind of impact they are having on all aspects of society, including economic, social, and environmental. (Source - Investopedia)

According to the *United Nations Industrial Development Organisation*, “Corporate social responsibility is a management concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and interactions with their stakeholders. CSR is generally understood as being the way through which a company achieves a balance of economic, environmental and social imperatives (Triple-Bottom-Line Approach), while at the same time addressing the expectations of shareholders and stakeholders. In this sense it is important to draw a distinction between CSR, which can be a strategic business management concept, and charity, sponsorships or philanthropy. Even though the latter can also make a valuable contribution to poverty reduction, will directly enhance the reputation of a company and strengthen its brand, the concept of CSR clearly goes beyond that.”

In India we see the business organisations have done philanthropic services since years and the Indian Business Houses have never looked back as far as giving support to the needy and victims of catastrophes. Then what is the need for CSR? And the answer is - CSR can be looked as an essential part of India's desire for development. It reaffirms country's commitment to include even those sections of the society in the growth process, which had remained excluded until now from the mainstream of development. The inclusion of CSR by the Government is an attempt to propagate national development agenda by engaging the businesses. With the introduction of CSR there is a legal obligation for the companies to take initiatives towards Social, Environmental and Economic Responsibilities.

Review of Literature

The Research Study was made to find out the impact or benefits which are derived by the Indian Business Houses out of compliance of CSR initiatives and for the same the following Research Papers were reviewed:

Goel, A. (2021), concluded that from past the business houses are incorporated for profit maximisation and there is a need that these entities are made responsible not only in contributing a part of its profits towards social welfare but should also take active participation in social and environment responsibilities.

Saxena, N. (2021), concluded that the Government is responsible for the implementation of CSR programs by providing Legal as well as Administrative Support to the Business Entities. The Government should ensure to carry out more and more projects of Infrastructure development taking the help of the Business Entities through the Government and Business Partnerships.

Khanchandani, V. (2021), concluded that E Governance is the solution to the multiple problems faced by the Citizens in India and for securing a good E Governance it is vital that we have Our Libraries which open for General Public to create an awareness and through the utilisation of the CSR programs such libraries can be started on a large scale.

Singh, K., & Misra, M. (2021), concluded that CSR in India can be adopted in the famous concept of John Moore's Ecosystem by combining the CSR with Ecosystem, making it a CSR Ecosystem whereby the Firms thrive to create a coordination between the Government and the Infrastructure Providers.

Mishra, L. (2021), concluded that CSR can be looked from the point of view of the Sustainable Development and if the Government of India or for that matter any Governments in the World wanted to achieve development goals then they must stress on the need for the Sustainable Development and for which the use of the funds of CSR contributions can be achieved.

Hosseini-Motlagh, S. M., Jazinaninejad, M., & Nami, N. (2021), concluded that the responsibility of CSR can be or should be clubbed with the Social factors or Social problems like managing the Medical waste generated by the Medicine manufacturing companies and disposal of those out of date medicines or medical apparatus through a sound system so that it do not result in harm to the general public as well as the environment.

Objectives and Research Methodology:

To analyse and check the impact created or the Goodwill generated by the Indian Companies or any recognition given by the Government or Government Departments for sincerely contributing to the CSR.

Also, to throw a light on the vital aspect for which no research papers or analysts have

concentrated that is the basic purpose of CSR is not Philanthropy or Charity but is to share the responsibility of Nation Building along with the Government and if the Companies have done that then there should be an appreciation and acknowledgment at the appropriate forums and from the appropriate persons that is the Government Publications, Government Departments as well as the Government itself. If the credit for any projects is taken by the Ruling party of the State or the Centre then there should be an equal recognition and credit be given to all those companies contributing towards the CSR and funds out of such CSR utilised for those projects.

For the above Research, I have considered Secondary Data only that is the Books, Periodicals, Journals and the Bare Acts published by the Government Departments.

Based on the above analysis, I have drawn a conclusion that the Government or the Government Departments have failed to put efforts in recognising the role played by the industries in contributing to the Nation Building through contributions to the CSR. In fact no public document can be found which specifies that which public project involves how much contributions out of CSR contributed by the companies.

Analysis and Findings

The following analysis is found:

Legal Provisions as per the Companies Act,2013:

As per the provisions of Section 135 of the Companies Act,2013, every company having a net worth of Rupees 500 crore or more, a Turnover of Rupees 1000 or more, or a Net Profit of Rupees 5 crore or more in a financial year is supposed to constitute a corporate social responsibility committee comprising of at least 3 Directors of which at least 1 should be Independent Director. The CSR committee is supposed to formulate and recommend a CSR policy which should be based on the activities specified in Schedule VII of the Companies Act,2013, and recommend the amount of expenses to be incurred and also monitor the implementation of CSR policy from time to time. The Board of every company falling under the provisions of Section 135 shall ensure that the company spends at least 2% of the average net profits the company earned during the 3 preceding financial years. Besides that,the companies are supposed to utilise its CSR funds only through the Agencies which fulfill the criteria specified under the Rules or through the Government Agencies.

Schedule VII of the Companies Act, 2013 specifies the following activities:

a) Eradicating extreme hunger and poverty, Malnutrition, preventive health care and

sanitation, availability of safe drinking water.

- b) Promotion of education, Special education and vocational skill enhancement especially among women, elderly, differently abled.
- c) Promoting gender equality and empowering women, Setting up homes and hostels for women and orphans, setting up old age homes, day care centres and other facilities for senior citizens.
- d) Reducing child mortality and improving maternal health.
- e) Combating human immunodeficiency virus, acquired immune deficiency syndrome, malaria and other diseases.
- f) Ensuring environmental sustainability, Ecological balance, protection of flora and fauna, animal welfare, agroforestry, conservation of natural resources and maintaining quality of soil, air and water.
- g) Employment enhancing vocational skills.
- h) Social business projects, Contribution or funds provided to technology incubators located within academic institutions which are approved by the Central Government
- i) Contribution to Prime Minister's Relief Fund or any other fund set up by the central government or state governments for socio-economic development and relief and funds for the welfare of the Scheduled Castes, the Scheduled Tribes, other backward classes, minorities and women
- j) Such other matters as may be prescribed.
- k) Protection of national heritage, art and culture including restoration of buildings and sites of historical importance and works of art, setting up public libraries, promotion of traditional arts and handicrafts.
- l) Measures for the benefit of armed forces veterans, war widows and their dependents, Central Armed Police Forces (CAPF) and Central Para Military Forces (CPMF) veterans, and their dependents including widows.
- m) Training to promote rural sports, nationally recognized sports, Paralympic sports and Olympic sports.
- n) Rural development projects.

Contributions made by Indian companies under CSR provisions (Source CSR Yearbook by CRISIL)

Within just 7 years since CSR was made mandatory, spending on corporate social responsibility in India has crossed the Rs 1 lakh crore milestone, with around 40% of this incurred in the past two years as companies helped the country fight Covid-19 pandemic. The overall CSR spending in fiscal 2020 was at Rs 21,231 crore, with 1,387 listed companies accounting for Rs 14,431 crore (26% more than in fiscal 2019), and 19,962 unlisted ones @ Rs 6,800 crore (7% less than in fiscal 2019). In fiscal 2021, assuming the spending was around the mandated mark of 2% of average profit of the preceding three fiscals, eligible companies would have spent Rs 22,000 crore on CSR, including Rs 14,986 crore by more than 1,700 listed ones and Rs 7,072 crore by unlisted entities.

We found the analysis based on data sourced from company websites, public disclosures and articles/ features on reliable websites, including those of top newspapers, business magazines and financial portals. CSR is on an upward trajectory in terms of spending and reporting.

Among sectors, manufacturing, energy and financial services accounted for over 60% of the spending. Public sector companies (accounting for 7% of the total eligible companies) contributed 32% of the total CSR spending, while private ones (accounting for 87% of total eligible companies) spent 63%

ISO 26000 – Social Responsibility:

This is a guidance tool provided by the ISO which informs the organisations to understand the meaning and significance of social responsibility and encourages them to comply with these responsibilities honestly. It is important to note that this is not a certification like any other ISO certification but is only a guiding tool. Organisations which comply with these standards are self-certified. Six core areas of social responsibility include (i) human rights (ii) labour practices (iii) environment (iv) fair operating practices (v) consumer issues (vi) community involvement and development. This assures a sincere approach to the concept of social responsibility and sustainable development.

Efforts on the part of Government to recognise or appreciate the efforts put up by Companies by contributing towards CSR and help in Nation Building:

No such efforts were found on the part of Government. In fact, during the Research I have found that the contributions made by the companies towards the CSR were found or collected from the Financial Statements published by the companies. Neither the Government has established any ISO kind certification whereby the people can know

which companies are complying with the CSR provisions on regular basis and which companies are not. Nor the Government has mentioned that while contributing to the Flood or other disaster reliefs how much money was spent out of the contributions through CSR. Not a single Government Letter or communication is sent to any of these companies sincerely contributing towards the Nation Building. We, the people of India do know the philanthropies done by the Big Business houses like Tatas, Birla or Ambani but we hardly know the contributions made even a small company having a net profit of only rupees 50 crores and contributing rupees 1 crore towards the CSR as the amount is too small or insignificant in the eyes of media to take note or recognise it. But one should not forget that even such a small contribution from hundreds of companies would result in a huge pool of funds which can definitely change, modify or affect the lives of a few hundreds or thousands.

In fact, we have the provisions whereby the defaulting companies are penalised for failure to comply towards the CSR spending, namely,

Substituted by the Companies (Amendment) Act, 2020:

Section 135(7) If a company is in default in complying with the provisions of sub-section (5) or sub-section (6) of the Companies Act,2013, the company shall be liable to a penalty of twice the amount required to be transferred by the company to the Fund specified in Schedule VII or the Unspent Corporate Social Responsibility Account, as the case may be, or one crore rupees, whichever is less, and every officer of the company who is in default shall be liable to a penalty of one-tenth of the amount required to be transferred by the company to such Fund specified in Schedule VII, or the Unspent Corporate Social Responsibility Account, as the case may be, or two lakh rupees, whichever is less.

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